

REASONS RAISING THE CONCEPT “MAN” IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY

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Abstract. As far as we know a stereotype is a phrase relating to all the members of class. The term is often used with a negative connotation when referring to an oversimplified, exaggerated or demeaning assumption that a particular individual possesses the characteristics associated with the class due to his or her membership in it. Stereotypes can be used to deny individuals respect or legitimacy based on their membership in that group. Stereotypes often form the basis of prejudice and are usually employed to explain real or imaginary differences due to race, gender, religion, and ethnicity, and socio-economic class, disability, and occupation. In stereotypes men's role is very great. The main idea of this paragraph based on gender differences in English phraseology. Defining their role in society with the women currently is not so differ, because some men are being feminine who want to have the same feel like women do. But, in the first paragraph it was given the reasons of their being in such position, and shown the right way of men's behavior. It was analyzed that men should follow such rules from which women can observe their masculinity. I think, the extraordinary men's position can influence to the relations with the women. These types of problems have been existing for years and some men's bad acts are expressed with the phrases in oral speech. Such phrases are added to the paragraph and analyzed in detail.

Key words Stereotype, race, gender, religion, and ethnicity, and socio-economic class, disability, masculinity

Introduction There are many reasons of raising the concept of “man” in phraseology. Through these phrases we may easily understand the culture and out world of other nations, because these phrases are based on the customs, traditions and stereotypical approaches of this nation. So, in the phraseological unities with the concept “man” we may realize the stereotypical views of nations. But year by year notion may change its meaning and of course it will depend on social position of man in a society or in family. To analyze exact reasons, the questionnaire was taken from opposite gender members. These

questions will identify men's and women's features and let us analyze phrases with gender peculiarities.

The following questions were given to female, male to describe the same gender members and opposite ones:

1. Characteristic features.
2. Activity.
3. Attitude to labor.
4. Negative qualities.
5. Appearance.
6. Comments.

The answers were like:

Female Description of "woman"

1. Sometimes naughty, sometimes obedient (2), curious (3), clever (6), sophisticated, kind(3), mild (5), weak, easy-going (2), strong, loyal, reliable, brave(3), hard working (3).
2. Hard working (10), active (8), stubborn, optimist (1).
3. Loves working (20), sometimes lazy (2)
4. Thinks about all but not themselves (2), likes to cry (5), sly (2), Light minded (3), lazy (2), believable (6), likes gossip (7) .
5. Attractive (6), pretty, beautiful (7), slim (5), graceful (2) .
6. In one word women are weaker than men. Women like with ears, she needs caress as baby needs milk.

They are the strongest and the weakest creature in the world.

Male description of "woman"

1. Patient, pertinent, polite, kind (6), egoist (5), eligible, housewife (10), mother (7), screamer (9), chatterbox(5), actress (7).
2. Energetic, hard working (3), accurate (2), very active (3).
3. Tidy (3), responsible (5), workaholic (6).
4. Furious (4), jealous (6), impolite, rude(4), keen on richness (5), likes gossips
5. Pretty (6), slim, beautiful, well clothed.
6. Man can't live without woman. Woman attracts man with her charm and glory. Man misses woman like the desert misses the rain.

Male description of "man"

1. Serious (7), respectable (4), punctual, social, active, brave (7), concrete (5), kind (4), keeps his words (6)
2. Communicative, scientist, chairman, energetic, hard working, fast (2)
3. Responsible, skillful (6), hard working (7), talented (4)

4. Drinks, smokes (20), furious (10), Impertinent, jealous (10)
5. Handsome, good looking (15)
6. Men are in the corner of attention with their positive qualities.

Female Description of “man”

1. Brave (10), decisive, generous (4), hardworking (7), intelligent (6), protective (5), strong (5)
2. Fast, active (5), guardian (9), energetic (3)
3. Passive (15), responsible (5), slow (3)
4. Stupid, likes to be false to his wife, pessimist (3), drinks (15)
5. Handsome (20), strong, cute (15)
6. Male loves with his eyes. He feeds the mouths.

These responds prescribe the real position and duties of man in a family and society.

Some of responders used the following proverbs and idioms to describe a man: A man of words & not of deeds is like a garden full of weeds;

The answer to a maiden's prayer- appeared to describe a man with all qualities what a woman wants

A bag of winds- a man who talks too much and doesn't do anything

Bring home the bacon – to succeed in one's life

Many phraseological units have etymological originations. A good example is the German idiom, seinen Hut nehmen in English “to take one's hat” means to resign from one's post, office, to step down (referring to men). The inner form of this idiom is based on a physical action. In former times, middle class men used to wear a hat in public. They had to take the hat off entering a room. If a man was leaving he took his hat and the expression denoting this action developed the meaning “to leave a group, to say good bye” (cf Rohrich, 1991: 776). Of course, women also wore hats in public, but were not obliged to take them off when entering a room. Therefore, a woman who was going to leave didn't take her hat.

The consequence is that this idiom was originally restricted in its use and referred exclusively to males. Though the custom of wearing a hat in public has changed and the action of “taking the hat” no longer is of any importance, the gender – specific restriction of this expression still has an impact on its usage. The restriction to males clearly emerges from frequency analysis. Among more than 500 text examples drawn from the Internet only one example has been found with reference to a woman, to be precise, to a female minister.

The text examples reveal another peculiarity of this idiom; the person resigning as socially important and their resignation has to have some consequences for a given social group. Either they come from a higher occupational group, such as ministers, directors, managers, chairmen and the like, or they are, e.g., a popular sportsman leaving a club. This usage restriction can be interpreted as correlating with the etymology. The etymologically relevant feature "belonging to the middle class" (wearing a hat was left up to middle class men) corresponds with the social importance of the resigning person. So the elements of etymological knowledge (labeled here "etymological memory") may have synchronic relevance.

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